

Sonification for Process Monitoring in Highly Sensitive Surgical Tasks

¹Sasan Matinfar, ²Thomas Hermann, ³Matthias Seibold,
³Philipp Frnstahl, ³Mazda Farshad, ¹Nassir Navab

¹ Computer Aided Medical Procedures, Technical University of Munich, Germany

² Ambient Intelligence Group, CITEC & Faculty of Technology, Bielefeld University, Germany

³ Department of Orthopaedics, Balgrist University Hospital, University of Zurich, Switzerland.

sasanmatinfar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Surgeons usually have to keep track of many variables during a surgical intervention. This paper introduces three novel sonification approaches for fluid-related process data monitoring in the highly sensitive surgical context. From the instantaneous fluid (creation or expenditure) rate, different feature time series have been computed, including the cumulative fluid volume or filtered signals, which are in turn used for a set of sonification methods that structure a composed soundscape, either natural, musical or hybrid in real-time. We present 3 variations of 3 approaches with introductory example videos, each followed by results of a first user study in search of the preferred/most acceptable auditory representations. The qualitative evaluation of our method shows the potential for further research in this field.

1. INTRODUCTION

The advancements in computer technology have enabled the automatic collection of a vast amount of multi-modal data intra-operatively, i.e., during the course of medical intervention such as surgery. The problem is that the current limitations of display technology for the operating clinician lead to the situation that a considerable part of these data are either missing for the surgical team or cannot be perceived intra-operatively. One reason for this problem is that in the modern operating rooms, visual media have been used as the main approach to presenting the information. Yet sometimes it is difficult or even impossible to use visual monitors for data display. First, because the surgeons would then be forced to constantly switch their focus of attention between patient and monitor; Second, even by using virtual displays in AR, the overlay of many different visual cues occludes the field of view, which can cause the well-known inattentive blindness [1]. These are also the relevant problems in situations where monitoring of real-time data is merely the secondary task and the display persists during the entire time of the surgery.

Sonification, the systematic auditory display of data by using sound [2] offers many possibilities for addressing this problem. The omnidirectional propagation of sound does not require the user to attend to a specific location and they can thus focus on their primary task while perceiving peripheral information. This feature helps us to improve the problem of missing data during the surgery, i.e., information can be processed without requiring to shift the visual focus of attention. However, an important question here is how sonifications for process monitoring should be implemented - both from the aesthetics and individual preferences point of view, so that, particularly in a sensitive situation such as a surgery, it provides an information system which is at the same time ergonomic, informative, and workable. This will be more challenging and critical when the data is multidimensional.

In this paper, we propose three novel approaches to sonify a surgical signal, in particular, for a fluid-related signal. Fluid-related signals are measurements of the expenditure, loss, or consumption of fluid during the intervention. They are typically continuous signals and practical constraints may demand to stay within safe limits of either the instantaneous rate or the integral over the whole intervention. For this paper, we keep our detailed application scenario undisclosed to better generalize for the broader category of these situations. For our sonification methods presented here, we propose different signal processing approaches and generate different signals from a single initial signal to create a richer signal space for an "orchestrated" multi-stream sonification. We applied different kinds of filters, such as the moving average over different periods. Then, we mapped the parameters of the resulting features to sound, using Parameter Mapping Sonification (PMSon). The key idea in this approach is not only providing the original signal but to present additional information streams such as the accumulated signal and moving averages as well. Creating three variants for three approaches we obtained nine sonification types. We evaluated the resulting nine sonifications in a preliminary qualitative user study to determine aesthetics, compatibility with the main task, and to identify the best sonifications designs.

2. RELATED WORK

Sonification approaches for process monitoring are well established in the Auditory Display community. The applications are ranging from complex event-based situations

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such as network traffic to production processes [3]. In the following, we provide a brief overview of systems that deal with monitoring as a secondary task.

Hermann et al. [4] proposed an audio-visual system for monitoring, querying and accessing information of different modules or processes in complex systems. They computed the emotional information of the processes and communicated them using sounds according to the emotional status of the process. For this approach, they used Musical Sonification and Model-Based Sonification.

Hildebrandt et al. [5] proposed a multi-modal approach for monitoring business processes using sonification to enhance conventional monitors and information systems which are depending mainly on the visual displays. In [6], they have been analyzed the business process monitoring tasks and the data structure in this field to build a foundation. According to this analysis, the usage of sonification for similar data structure has been studied so they summarized them in a list of recommendations that can be considered as guidelines for sonification of similar data.

Hildebrandt et al. [7] have demonstrated the advantages of continuous sonification: in a subjective experiment, they compared different peripheral process monitoring systems (visual only, visual + auditory alarm, and continuous sonification). Their comparison was based on the reaction time and the error-rate of the users by recognizing the events as they focus on and perform their primary task. Their results show that their continuous sonification for process monitoring, using a data-driven forest soundscape, significantly benefits the timing of attentional shifts towards the monitored system, as they become *anticipation optimal*.

EEG and anesthesia-machine are the established surgical sonification examples which have been already integrated into the surgical routines. Moreover, there have been several works for surgical sonification [8, 9], however, they have mainly focused on navigational tasks.

Matinfar et al. [10, 11], proposed a sonification approach for communicating peripheral information in a surgical task, in particular for ophthalmic surgery. The suggested approach conveys the information about the existence of the surgical tool in three discrete labeled area in the ocular cavity i.e. normal, careful, dangerous. The method can be considered as Event-Based PMSon since it notifies the surgeon as the tool entered a new area through the online modifications of a music stream.

In this context, the main task (performing surgery on a patient) is a critical and highly sensitive situation where the operator is completely focused and might be stressed. Because the result of her/his work directly affects human life, the sonification must be ergonomic, distinctive, and informative to best support the surgeon's work. At the same time, it should not be boring or annoying over long-term tasks, e.g. for an operation that lasts more than 3 hours.

3. APPLICATION SCENARIOS

The application scenario is a medical intervention over an extended time where the use, loss, or consumption or change of properties of one or more fluids is relevant to the success of the intervention [12, 13], we call the general

class *fluid-based signal sonification*. The data are mostly continuous signals and practical constraints demand to stay within safe limits of either the instantaneous rate or the integral over the whole intervention. This type of information exists, for instance, in water loss, transpiration, urination, wound water, etc. as fluids; as well the pulse oximeter, for instance, is also concerned with a fluid signal, namely the oxygen saturation in the blood.

Specific to fluid-based signal sonifications is that fluids are usually incompressible, they change with a rate, and accumulate, either in loss or production. So relevant features are the integral over time, the actual rate, the change of the rate over time, the sign of the rate relating to whether the fluid is growing or depleting, and few other features that matter to the specific application scenario. Sometimes it might be interesting to have the integral over a relevant time interval to stay within healthy bounds, e.g. to avoid dehydration, and there could be different intervals that matter to different medical personal (anaesthetist, surgeon, etc.).

As several derived/relevant features are available, we decided, in line with experiences and recommendations from the above-cited related work, to create a multi-stream sonification, i.e., features that influence the sonic shape of a corresponding auditory stream. Specifically, we decided to use natural soundscape sounds and musical streams. The reason is that users must be able to process the sonifications at a low cognitive load since they need to focus on their primary task, so the sonification should only create an awareness of the signals and their temporal progression. The challenge, however, is to combine all the features and constraints into a working auditory display.

4. DATA REPRESENTATION

For this paper we use the variable δ (*delta*) as scalar variable to refer to the instantaneous rate of fluid flow, i.e. the loss or creation as measured by a sensor at a certain rate. For our project, we measured δ at a sampling rate of 1 Hz. Alternatively it can also be determined by subtraction of the current and previous accumulated amount of fluid by

$$\delta(t) = \frac{V(t) - V(t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t}. \quad (1)$$

By *volume* $V(t)$ we understand the accumulated *delta*, i.e., the integral over *delta* from beginning to time t as

$$\text{volume} = V(t) = \int_0^t \delta(t) dt. \quad (2)$$

The *volume* at time $t = n$ is the total accumulated amount of *delta* from $t = 0$ to $t = n$. **FIR** or Finite Impulse Response in signal processing characterizes filters whose impulse response is of finite duration, i.e., it settles to zero in a finite time. In this project, we applied FIR filters to the *delta* signal to obtain smooth features which average the instantaneous signal and do not introduce significant noise (s. Fig. 2).

Moving Average (MA), also called moving mean or rolling mean is a type of FIR. Here, we used the simple *MA*

which is simply the unweighted average of a fixed-size subset of a series of numbers. The *MA* at time t for the time period τ is the average over all t values from $t - \tau$ to t divided by the τ :

$$\text{MA}(t) = \frac{1}{\tau} \left(\sum_{k=t-\tau}^t \delta(k) \right) \quad (3)$$

where the parameter τ determines the averaging time period.

5. SONIFICATION METHODS

The sonification technique used for this project is PMSon, and in particular in some parts Event-Based PMSon, based on different combinations of the signals as shown in Table 1. The mappings have been introduced in detail in Section 4, and for each signal combination, we proposed a specific approach as described below.

NSS	DDAC	CSSIS
MA 5s	delta	MA 30s
MA 30s	filtered-delta	MA 120s
MA 120s	volume	filtered-delta
volume		volume

Table 1: signal combinations in three sonification categories, see the text for abbreviations. We called *delta* filtered by FIR shortly *filtered-delta*.

We developed our sonifications in three major categories:

- Category 1: Natural Soundscape Sonification (NSS);
- Category 2: Data-driven Algorithmic Composition (DDAC);
- Category 3: Combined Soundscape & Synthetic Information Streams (CSSIS).

The sounds have been chosen according to aesthetic reasons and we cannot prove or claim that they are the best possible sounds for stream segregation or adoption by surgeons. Please see videos V1–V9, available as supplementary material at DOI:10.4119/unibi/2938433, which present and explain these sonifications with synchronized visualization of signal and features.

5.1 Natural Soundscape Sonification

This group included three sonifications, NNS-1–NNS-3, with different mappings (see V1–V3), and all of them have been implemented only based on natural sound samples from environmental soundscapes, such as shaking water, rain sounds, bird songs, seagull songs, etc. The signal combination in this group was the *MA* with different τ values namely 5, 30, 120 seconds, and the *volume* as depicted in Figure 1.

Everybody is familiar with natural sounds from sonic contexts, such as holidays, walks, work, etc. In this work,

Figure 1: signal setup by NSS, threshold=0.75; x-axis depicts time in seconds, y-axis shows the fluid rate in arb. units. e.g. millilitre.

we want to investigate the impact of such intuitive sounds for process monitoring of highly sensitive surgical tasks.

In all three sonifications of this group, the *MA* of $\tau = 5s$ in the domain of $[0, 4]$ has been mapped to the sound level and the rate of the water shake sample. Note that rate 1Hz refers to the original recording, 0.5Hz and 2Hz are half resp. 2 times the speed, i.e. an octave lower resp. higher.

The other *MA*s, with $\tau = 30s$ within $[0, 2]$ and $\tau = 120s$ within $[0, 1]$, have been mapped in each example differently. In the NSS-1 (V1), the *MA* $\tau = 30s$ and *MA* $\tau = 120s$ have been mapped to the samples of seagulls and motor boat. In NSS-2 and NSS-3, the *MA* $\tau = 30s$ has been mapped to the parameters of the birds sample; whereas, the *MA* with $\tau = 120s$ in NSS-2 has been mapped to a sample of horse, and in NSS-3 to the recorded sounds of rain. The details of the mappings in all nine sonifications is available in the appendix in the supplementary material DOI:10.4119/unibi/2938433. More details on the mapping parameters in NSS-3 illustrated in Table 2.

(a) MA 5s [0, 4]	
water shake	level [-14, 0] dB, rate [1, 4] Hz
(b) MA 30s [0, 2]	
birds	level [-12, 0] dB, rate [1, 2.5] Hz
(c) MA 120s [0.25, 1]	
rain	level [-20, -4.5] dB rate [0.6, 1.2] Hz, pan [1, 0]

Table 2: Mapping details for NNS-3

Besides, we have defined a threshold for the *MA* of $\tau = 30s$, triggering a dedicated sound sample whenever that level is exceeded. Exceeding the threshold in NSS-1 and NSS-3 has been signaled with a thunder sound sample, and in NNS-2 with a herd of sheep. The rising *volume* (i.e., integral of *delta*) has been signaled every 50 ml by church bell strikes in all three sonifications.

The entire source and output values have been clipped to the given ranges, and all the mappings were linear.

5.2 Data-driven Algorithmic Composition

The sonifications of this group, DDAC-1–DDAC-3, have been composed based on the rule-based and stochastic techniques. The compositions have been created based on the synthesized instruments¹ such as a reverb, a musical pad, randomized melodic patterns of the marimba, and numbers of percussive strokes of a bell (V4–V6). The input signals *delta*, *filtered-delta*, and *volume* control a bunch of different parameters of the instruments. The signal mix is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: signal setup by DDAC, threshold=1; x-axis depicts time in seconds, y-axis shows the fluid rate in arb. units, e.g., millilitre.

The DDAC examples followed a similar concept of mapping, i.e., in all three variants each signal controls the same parameter, however, each time with different parameter levels. Thus, they create a different intensity in the whole sound texture. *Delta* within [0, 10] ml controlled inter-onset variations in the pad, and parameters such as frequency, detune, cutoff-frequency, and sound level in marimba. On the other hand, *volume* changes within the domain of [0, 250] ml have been reflected in the parameters of the reverb (mix, pre-delay, level, and pre-delay-time) and marimba (attack, sustain, release, reciprocal quality). Finally, exceeding the threshold = 1 by *filtered-delta* triggered the bell strikes of different times in each sonification example.

The sequence of marimba notes exhibits rhythmical similarity with the granular texture when a fluid (e.g. rain) drops on a solid surface (e.g. metal surface). Hence, the sonification using musical sounds can activate a metaphoric association to dripping fluid, allowing users, in turn, to infer more easily properties such as the density of grains. As the *delta* value increases, the rhythmical pattern and the tempo get faster and more disordered. The details of the mappings in DDAC-2 are shown in Table 3. All the source and output values have been clipped to the given ranges and the mappings were linear.

5.3 Combined Soundscapes & Synthetic Information Streams

The examples of this group, CSSIS-1–CSSIS-3, built a hybrid combination of previously introduced mapping ideas,

¹ All instruments in this project have been synthesized in SuperCollider, inspired by github.com/elifieldsteel/Supercollider3_tutorials_code

(a) *delta* [0, 10] in ml/s

pad	inter-onset[random(4.5-5.5), random(0.5-1.5)] s
marimba	inter-onset [random(0.99-1), random(0.1-0.2)] s frequency [1, 3] Hz detune [0, 15] Hz cutoff [1, 5] Hz level [-26, -3] dB pan [random(0-0), (-1-1)]

(b) *filtered-delta* [1, 4]

bell	3x strikes
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(c) *volume* [0, 250] in ml

marimba	rq* [random(0.005, 0.008), random(0.09, 0.2)] attack [3, 1.5] s sustain [1, 0.5] s release [5, 2.5] s
reverb	reverb-time [1.8, 0.5] s mix [0.5, 0.1] predelay [0.4, 0.1] s level [-2, -14] dB

Table 3: mapping details in DDAC-2; *rq stands for reciprocal quality.

i.e. some of the signals have been mapped to the natural soundscape sounds whereas others have been mapped to music parameters. The general idea of music has emerged by randomizing the melodic patterns based on the Japanese scale *Hirajoshi*². The signal collection in this group consisted of *filtered-delta*, the MA with $\tau = 30s$ and $\tau = 120s$ as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: signal setup by CSSIS; x-axis depicts time in seconds, y-axis shows the fluid rate in arb. units, e.g. millilitre.

The *filtered-delta* within [0, 4] has been mapped to the sound level and the rate of water shake sample in CSSIS-1 (V7), birds in CSSIS-2 (V8), and both water shake and

² With note C as the root, the scale is C E F# G B

birds in CSSIS-3 (V9).

The MA 30s in the domain of [0, 2] has been mapped, in various combinations, to different musical parameters such as sound level and tempo of a randomized melodic pattern based on the Japanese scale. The melodies have been played by different instrument combinations such as *Guzheng*, *Pipa*³, and synthesized marimba. All mapping details are detailed in the supplementary material⁴.

Finally, the mappings of the MA with $\tau = 120s$ in the domain of [0, 1] were as follows: in CSSIS-1 to the sound level of the Bamboo flute; in CSSIS-2 to the sound level of the synthesized marimba; and in CSSIS-3 to the sound level and the rate of the rain sample.

The entire source and outputs have been clipped to the given ranges of the mapping functions while all the mappings were linear. The *volume* has been signalized in every 50 ml with the strikes of *Taiko*⁵ in CSSIS-1 and CSSIS-2, and with Japanese bell in CSSIS-3. The details of the mappings in CSSIS-1 are illustrated in Table 4.

(a) filtered-delta [0, 4]	
water shake	level [-20, 0] dB, rate [1, 3] Hz
(b) MA 30s [0, 2]	
melodic pattern	by values > 0.5 : Guzheng: level [-40, -6] dB by values > 0.75 : Pipa: level [-40, -10] dB
(c) MA 120s [0, 1]	
Bamboo	by values > 0.45 : level [-26, -14] dB

Table 4: mapping details in CSSIS-1

6. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

We report results of the first step in a two-step quantitative evaluation: step one is the aesthetic and pragmatic evaluation at hand of regular listeners – in order to keep the precious and limited time of the target group of surgeons reserved for step two: the assessment of pre-selected sonification types with the target group.

In the first step, we conducted a qualitative questionnaire study including 9 videos. Each video (≈ 2 minutes) presented one sonification example including the visual presentation of the corresponding signals. The videos consisted of the manually selected highlights of the signal flow. After watching each video, the participants (10 non-experts in music, sound design, or medicine) were asked to express their degree of agreement to 12 statements (resp. questions) using the Likert scale format. The sequence of the videos was reordered anew for each participant. We aimed at identifying the best-rated sonification

³ *Guzheng* and *Pipa*, both are the traditional Japanese instruments.

⁴ DOI:10.4119/unibi/2938433

⁵ *Taiko* refers to a broad range of traditional Japanese percussion instruments.

example in each category for our further optimization and subsequent quantitative studies with the target group. The 12 questions include: 6 questions on how useful, recognizable, pleasant etc. (positive features); 4 questions on how distracting, annoying etc. (negative features) the system was; and the last 2 questions on how long they would estimate to listen to the sonifications in both passive and active modes (questionnaire available in appendix). The participants were asked to give a grade to each question. We gave each response from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree" respectively from 1 to 5 points by positive features, and vice versa by negative features. Their estimated time of listening has been pointed from 1 to 5 for a range between "less than 5 minutes" and "more than 60 minutes". The average and statistic error are shown in Table 5.

NSS-1		NSS-2		NSS-3	
34.9	2.25	30.8	2.55	42.7	2.41
DDAC-1		DDAC-2		DDAC-3	
39.7	2.38	40.0	2.75	38.3	2.48
CSSIS-1		CSSIS-2		CSSIS-3	
41.7	2.31	41.6	2.73	38.9	1.95

Table 5: the average (left) and standard error (right) for each example; sonifications with the highest average in each category highlighted.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Although, our preliminary evaluation was not meant to statistically prove the significant effects of our method on recognition of signals and the reaction time, yet they guide us for our future study. The average point in all the examples is above 50% of the maximum possible 60 points, this means that our system has been positively accepted by the participants, especially according to the subjective features such as pleasantness or annoyance (please note that by features such as annoyance, which have negative impact, we inverted the scale so that higher values refer to better impact). This is important since the subjective preferences of the surgical crew affect the acceptance of the system in such cases. Listening to music, e.g. on the radio during surgery is a common practice by many surgeons and in many hospitals. So integrating information into a pleasant, engaging, and not annoying music stream could help bringing valuable information into the surgical routine in a convenient way.

To identify the best candidates in each category, we performed an analysis of variance (ANOVA) for each category separately. The result of ANOVA using $\alpha = 0.05$ fails to reject the null hypothesis for the groups DDAC and CSSIS which means we can't find a significant difference between the examples in any of both groups. However, the test rejects the null hypothesis by NSS and shows there is a candidate with a significant difference (see Table 6). Performing Bonferroni post-hoc for NSS results in that NSS-3 differs significantly from NSS-2 (Table 7 and Figure 4). This suggests NSS-3 as the best possible candidate in its category for further our studies.

category	F-statistic	PR(>F)
NSS	6.298162	0.005689
DDAC	0.127451	0.880863
CSSIS	0.456207	0.638478

Table 6: ANOVA shows there is an example by NSS whose average is significantly different from other groups.

compared groups	statistic	p-value
NSS-1 & NSS-2	1.2058	0.2435
NSS-2 & NSS-3	-3.389	0.0033
NSS-1 & NSS-3	-2.3601	0.0298

Table 7: Bonferroni correction post-hoc comparison. The p-value by NSS-2 & NSS-3 is less than the corrected p-value 0.0166, $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure 4: boxplot NNS-3

In summary, we presented nine variants of sonification methods for process monitoring of fluid time series as secondary tasks in highly sensitive primary task contexts. Based on our qualitative evaluation, we can assume that our approach of data-driven soundscapes has the potential for further study and quantitative evaluation of the error rates and reaction times in judging variables at random points in time.

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